

Vyttila 3, a new rice variety for acid saline areas

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Vyttila 3 has been released for acid saline areas of Kerala. The Vyttila 1/Taichung Native 1 cross yields 200 kg/ha more than improved pureline selection Vyttila 1.

Vyttila 3, with 115 d duration, is

Performance of Vyttila 3 in farmers' fields, Kerala, India.

Location	Yield (t/ha)	
	Vyttila 1	Vyttila 3
Parur	0.9	1.3
Vyttila	3.6	3.8
Maradu	2.4	2.4
Panangad	3.7	4.0
Chellanam	4.5	5.0
Kandekadavu	4.3	4.1
Kannamali	4.5	4.9
Mean	3.4	3.6

suitable for May-Jun to Sep-Oct (pokkali season) cultivation. It is 166 cm tall with 3.6 t/ha average yield potential and 5 t/ha maximum yield potential (see table). Kernels are red with good cooking quality; protein content is 7.8%.

The variety is photoperiod insensitive and tolerant of major diseases and most insect pests (except stem borer, leafroller, and rice bug). □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

TEMPERATURE TOLERANCE

Chhomro — a promising cold-tolerant traditional rice variety for rainfed wetlands in western hills in Nepal

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No improved rice varieties have yet been identified for temperate regions, particularly for elevations above 1,500 m. We evaluated 57 local varieties and 367 exotic materials during 1985-86. Local rices were collected from the altitude range 1,000-2,300 m in the western hills. Major sources of exotic materials were the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery (IRCTN), the National Cold Tolerance Rice Nursery (NCTRN), and an initial evaluation trial (IET) carried out in collaboration with the National Rice Improvement Programme (NRIP), Parwanipur.

Cold tolerance screening nurseries were established at LAC (1,500 m). Mean air temperatures during early seedling growth (Jun-Jul) were 16.2-17.1 °C minimum and 22.6-22.8 °C maximum. During ripening (Oct-Nov), minimum temperature was 9.9-15.2 °C and maximum was 16.7-20.1 °C. Maximum water temperature was 20.1 °C in Jul and 14.0 °C in Oct. Cold tolerance of local and exotic varieties was measured by leaf discoloration at seedling stage, spikelet sterility, and grain yield.

Table 1. Comparative performance of selected cold-tolerant rice varieties identified in different nurseries. LAC, 1985-86.

Trial or nursery	Best yielding varieties	Grain yield (t/ha) at 12% moisture content	Sterility ^d (%)	Cold injury at seedling stage ^e (1-9 scale)
Farmers' field, 1985 (n= 13)	Chhomro local	5.3	0	1
	Banahu local	5	.05	3
	Ghara local	3.4	15	3
NCTRN, 1985 (n = 30)	Laisika-F	4.2	20	3
	WR10072-79-1-2-3	2.4	25	3
	NR10068-60-3-2	2.2	25	4
IRCTN, 1985 (n = 184)	Laisika-I	5.1	5	3
	K39-96-1-1-1-2	4.9	5	4
NCTRN, 1986 (n = 22)	Chhomro local	4.8	0	1
	NR10073-167-3-1-3	4.1	30	4
	Phalame	3.4	60	4
LRCTN ^a , 1986 (n = 52)	Chhomro local	5.0	2	1
	Seto Bhakunde	3.9	2	2
	Kalo Patle	3.2	1	2
	Raksali	3.1	5	3
PON ^b , 1986 (n = 50)	Banahu local	4.1	6	2
	Chhomro local	4.0	5	1
	Raksali	2.8	10	3
SFT ^c , 1986 (n = 36)	Chhomro local	4.1	0	1

^a Local Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery. ^b Preliminary Observation Nursery. ^c Spacing × Fertility Trial on Chhomro local. ^d Spikelet sterility was estimated by eye and by grasping the panicle. ^e Measured according to the procedures mentioned in the IRRI *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale.

Table 2. Comparative performance of 2 best cold-tolerant local varieties of rice at an altitude of 1500 m.^a LAC, 1985-86.

Variety	Plant stand/m ²	Tillers/plant	Panicles/m ²	Grain yield ^b (t/ha)
Chhomro local	46.6 ± 3.27	7.0 ± 1.05	256.6 ± 34.71	4.798 ± 0.475
Raksali local	29.4 ± 4.48	5.6 ± 0.70	263.3 ± 52.30	2.359 ± 0.794
Difference (P = 0.05)	17.2 ns	1.4 ns	6.7 ns	2.439***

^a Yields were estimated from 1 m² crop cuts (n = 10) from seed multiplication block. ^b At 12% moisture content.